

operculum

for the protection of the environment

ecoboppers in action:
inspect '71
the reef.
the other tourists

price 50c

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for the fish and the snail, the operculum is a protective covering . . . *operculum* is a magazine for the protection of the environment.

operculum

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a compassionate commitment.....

Our Western agrarian civilization has given us many concepts that our hunting ancestors would have abhorred. The distinction between work and leisure, the intrinsic dignity of labor, hierarchical systems and the proletariat, and a view of man as a being outside nature are some such concepts. So ingrained are these that they are regarded as tenets rather than working assumptions. Genesis says God commanded man 'to be fruitful and multiply and fill the earth and subdue it, and have dominion over every living thing' and elsewhere man is told to 'go to the ant, thou sluggard: consider her ways and be wise' (Proverbs). Generally man seems to have been most obedient.

All of these beliefs are an affront to man's biological nature but today one of them is also very dangerous to his long-term survival—the belief that man is somehow outside nature.

Yesterday all these behaviour patterns had survival value despite their affrontery. This is easily seen in the flourishing of the societies that relied on them. But survival value does not exist in a vacuum, it is related to the environment, and this has changed as a result of our past successes in the pristine world.

Our success has changed our environment, but these changes could not have been foreseen yesterday because the elements that are now significant were not then imminent. Our agricultural way of life has allowed the human population to grow tremendously and has allowed our technology to expand. These two together have done much to alter the environment that once nurtured them.

It is in this past that we will discover the causes of the environmental problems of today. There is no one cause, just as there is no one section of society that can be held responsible. Our beliefs have led us to regard ourselves as the rulers of the world rather than as an important species in a fragile ecosystem. This cause, has led us away from the role of the prudent predator who husbanded his resources to the role of an unchecked exploiter.

The evergrowing number of people is also a cause in that it is this quantity of human protoplasm that is responsible for the great quantitative changes in the energy pathways of the ecosystem; while our technology compounds this as it is this force which is changing, qualitatively, our energy relationships with the rest of the biosphere.

These causes are inextricably connected, so that an

assault on one is buffered by the others. In order to change our relationship with the environment so that the former once again has survival value we need to change all three of these causes. This means individual commitment to all of them.

We need commitment to a new way of looking at our place in the world and to the logical consequences that follow from this new awareness. It is essential that this is on an individual basis because any national corporate ethos must be preceded by individual decisions.

It is not enough to argue that man is an integral part of this world yet give tacit support to those industries who act out their ecologically insane games with scarce resources. This may be emotionally comforting to the individual, but it is just this support that industry relies on to continue its present rapacious course.

It is also not enough to reach the intellectual plateau of the idea of population control and still insist on the validity of an economy rooted in the shadowy valley called populate or perish! And it is also not enough to condemn industrial polluters and yet not offer an ecologically sane alternative to their activities. Who will help industry change its methods if it is not the environmentalists?

We are all victims of our ecological crisis and so our commitment must extend throughout our society. Our technology must be made to fit our knowledge of the ecosystem, while recognizing that the technologists are only at fault in their acceptance of behaviour patterns common to us all. We should regulate our population to fit ecologically sensible goals and yet accept the dilemma of an overcrowded world in an humane way by not penalizing those who outstripped their resources before us.

As we re-order our beliefs to fit ecological constraints, we should, by recognizing the ingrained nature of many behaviour patterns, not treat harshly those who cannot change their anachronistic life styles just as we do not condemn our ancestors for their behaviour in their different world. These living fossils will be bypassed by the main stream of human affairs in this ecological decade. Let us regard their irrelevant behaviour with compassion even as we isolate them by our efforts to preserve the biosphere.

For, notwithstanding our respect for the past and those who cling to it, our commitment is to the future■

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ANZAAS

r. h. bradbury

ANZAAS—that pantechnicon—unloaded this year in Brisbane, and amongst the bag and baggage were some social issues. This new awareness of the rest of society is one of the most hopeful consequences of ANZAAS's reorganization of some short time ago. Since then it has spawned a vigorous new journal 'Search' which has carried many good articles on the impact of science on society. Such a change in behaviour for the scientific corpus may reflect the emergence to maturity and to positions of responsibility in the scientific establishment of those scientists who have grown up in the shadow of the Bomb.

The participation of these younger scientists on this ANZAAS congress showed that never again can science be divorced from its effects on society.

The environment crisis is probably the major area of this concern today, and environmentalists should be heartened somewhat in ANZAAS's response to it, for there were many symposia arranged on and around this problem.

However, ANZAAS is a strange thing—not at all like its counterparts overseas, for just as there seems to be no such thing as science in Australia, just merely lots of sciences; so too in ANZAAS are there scads of little empires all craving a piece of the action. One of the aims of ANZAAS is to overcome this specialization by bringing scientists of all disciplines together, but old jealousies and entrenched conservatism die hard in this country.

To be fair, ANZAAS does try by having intersectional symposia, but these are often overtly devoured by one section or they are at the level of polite exchanges as between in-laws.

Where does this leave high minded and intelligent discussion of the environment and its problems?—rather fragmented, really, and certainly rarely analytical or constructive. This fragmentation was compounded by the efforts of the numerous specialist societies who hold their own conferences at this time. They, too, were saying things about the environment, but with their own specialist viewpoint.

Such a barrage from such diverse sources left all but the most seasoned congress goers confused. There was even the final and official version of the ecology of the beaches courteously provided by the Rutile and Zircon Development Association Limited. It is comforting to know that these self-appointed guardians of our beaches have such a profound insight into ecological matters.

Lots of people talked about the environment. Some environmental biologists said that the problem was essentially a culture/ecology confrontation with disastrous consequences, but the anthropologists and sociologists weren't saying. Environmental scientists' ideas on culture may be a bit primitive (**for want of professional help**) but other scientists' ideas on just what that fashionable word, ecology, means had to be heard to be believed. The message of ecology as espoused by ecologists has just not got through to their scientific colleagues, let alone the public at large.

The moral of the congress becomes clear. For a few glorious days, engineers, botanists, chemists, economists, physicists and geographers have run their own little shows on the environment. This fragmentation helps explain the lack of an ecosystem approach; but, more than this, it shows that everyone is paying lip service to the environment crisis. In fact no scientist who wants public money can dare ignore it, so that this phenomenon is likely to gain momentum rather than lose it for the moment. But the message is not being pushed by ecologists (Ecological Society of Australia (—who?) please note). Stupid things are being passed off as ecology. This could emasculate the whole range of environment activity unless ecologists begin to speak out and define the real facts of the environment crisis immediately.

MT. ETNA *Continued from p. 50.*

It is apparent that until the thoughtless obsession with economic growth that our society follows is laid to rest then Mt Etna stood at the cross-roads. For Mt Etna could be "The Reef" (or any other part of our biosphere) and it is too much to suggest that conservationists prostitute their attitudes and argue that the Great Barrier Reef

should be saved because its structural diversity would provide an admirable base for nuclear powered submarines of the "future".

J. A. Harris

Zoology Department, University of Queensland.

commentary: the call of the wild

Dear Sir,

You ask for reader's comments, here are some. They relate to the first two contributions in the issue, by those Jobs' comforters Hegerl-Bradbury and Dwyer. I fully agree that we must spread the warning about the global environmental problem, but the solution to this, as stated, depends mainly on economic readjustment and population control, both complex long-term factors.

The layman, who we are trying to warn, may attempt a personal contribution to the latter problem but can do little about the former. There is therefore a danger of instilling a fatalistic feeling of helplessness when so much can be done on a limited scale. Such things as chasing the politicians (by voting switches) to implement pollution legislation, encouraging the technologists (by purchasing discrimination) to provide safer alternatives and in general following the excellent lines of your "saving the earth check-list". After all, conservation like charity should begin at home, and strong action in many local fields all helps to avert the final crisis.

Such individual action becomes all the more important when one considers the practical difficulties of population control—even aside from religious bigotry. The plethora of papers by demographers in "Science" and "Nature" over the last three years makes this plain. Japan has the most successful birth control programme in the world, but her population will not

level off till about 2030 and will then be circa 140 million. We have to find solutions (even stop-gap ones) to environmental deterioration now.

So by all means sound the tocsin, but please do not make it sound like a death knell.

Yours sincerely,

B. S. Newell.
Editor,
Australian Marine
Science Association
Bulletin.

Dear Sir,

Do you ever read fairy tales? I recently read one that was given to me by a friend. It's a beautifully written tale—profusely illustrated with delightful colour pictures of animals and birds, butterflies and trees and clear bubbling streams. It tells of unique Australian animals roaming safe and free in a land of compassionate people whose main concern appears to be to safeguard their precious heritage. The air is crisp and clear, and only goodness prevails . . . but, like all fairy tales . . . it just isn't true.

This delightful story, called "Heritage", was written and published by the Queensland State Public Relations Bureau. When I'd finished reading its last fascinating page I said to my friends: Y'know if all this were true, there'd be no need for conservationists! It was nothing more than a

well produced public relations effort to mislead the public into believing that our unique scenic areas are safe from despoilation—that pollution is under control—and that our wildlife never had it so good.

I understand that 80,000 copies of this booklet are to be distributed as a statement of fact to 7th and 8th grade students in this state. I was always under the impression that the word "education" implied a leading out of ignorance—not a deliberate deception.

Yours sincerely,
Charles C. Baines
State President
Save the Kangaroos
Committee

We hope to review "Heritage" in a coming issue of this magazine. (Ed.)

Dear Sir,

The Society is to be congratulated on the excellent quality of the journal "Operculum". Personally, I would like to see more articles of the type written by Francois Mergen and Dr Peter Dwyer, as I feel that the Q.L.S. should concentrate on these broader issues, as well as on specific aquatic issues.

Yours sincerely,
William J. Tearle
Garran Hall,
Australian National
University.